

On the economics of prostitution in sixteenth century Rome

Alexander Donald Stewart
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The material wealth of Rome started rising noticeably at the start of the sixteenth century, together with prostitution. In 1520 pope Leo X complained of 'licentious women who lead an ignoble and sordid life in the city we love, whose number (alas!) is increasing day by day due to the depravity of the times we live in [...]'. The Church, however, while admitting the immorality of prostitution, could not overlook the fact that some of these 'licentious' women, to judge from their luxurious life style, made money. Two decisions stemmed from these observations.

The first decision concerned taxation. The idea of a special tax arose when Pope Leo X ordered the construction of the a new, paved street, the Via Leonina (now called Via di Ripetta), and decided that the prostitutes of Rome should pay for it. This novel idea was reutilized in 1549 when the Ponte Santa Maria, originally built in ancient Roman times to carry the Via Aurelia across the Tiber, needed to be repaired. This time, however, the prostitutes to be taxed were recorded, and the tax roll survives in the Archivio di Stato di Roma. It is entitled *Tassa fatta alle cortigiane per la reparatione del ponte [di Santa Maria]*. It lists 436 women, states the annual rental they were assessed on, the tax paid (10% of the rental), and where they lived. The tax roll is particularly important because it is clear that *all* prostitutes were included, not just those that would today be thought of as courtesans (Mendoza 2016, p. 199). A summary list, based on the original manuscript, is given in Appendix 1.

The second decision was to establish a convent for repentant prostitutes, financed by a 20% death duty on those that insisted on continuing their 'licentious' careers. The duty was to be paid when they died. The decision was implemented by the bull *Salvator noster Jesus* published in 1520, establishing the convent in *rione* Colonna, close to the convent of San Silvestro. It was to be called the 'Monasterio delle Monache Convertite di Santa Maria Maddalena'. The legislative details of the foundation have been explored by Mendoza (2016, pp. 191–194).

The prostitutes of 1549

Much has been written about the lives of Roman courtesans of the sixteenth century. One thinks of Imperia Cognati (Petrucci 1982), Tullia d'Aragona (Hairston 2014), Julia da Gallese (Stewart 2025b), Isabella de Luna (Camerano 2022), and Fillide Melandroni (Bellini 2009). But what can be said of the other prostitutes, their clients, their location within the city, their incomes, and its effect on the economy of Rome? The 1549 tax roll (Appendix 1) provides some clues. It shows that almost all the women came from the districts of Campo Marzio, Ponte and Regola. There were a few from Colonna, Parione, Pigna and Sant'Eustachio, and none at all from Borgo, Trevi, Ripa, Campitelli, Monti, Sant'Angelo, and Trastevere (Figs. 1 & 2).

Fig. 1. Map showing the districts (*rioni*) of Rome in the sixteenth century. S. E. is Sant'Eustachio. Shaded areas indicate districts in which cardinals lived in 1527. The pope was in the Vatican (not shown), adjoining Borgo to the west.

Fig. 2. Map showing the distribution of the 420 Roman prostitutes in 1549, based on the tax roll of that year. Each black symbol represents ten individuals. The river Tiber is tinted grey. The Castel Sant'Angelo forms the eastern extremity of the district of Borgo. The only two bridges across the Tiber in the map area were then the Ponte Sisto and the Ponte Sant'Angelo.

Fig. 3. Histogram showing the distribution of rentals assessed on 369 Roman prostitutes in 1549, based on the tax roll of that year. The total number of women in the roll is 436, but for many of them no rent is specified. Quartile values in scudi; first quartile = 15, second (the median) = 22, third quartile = 34.

Of all the districts of the city, Campo Marzio stands out. In 1549 it had 184 prostitutes in a population which 30 years earlier, in 1527, was only 5282, i.e. 3.5%. This is twice the percentage in the adjoining districts of Ponte and Regola, which had together 236 prostitutes, inviting a comparison of Campo Marzio in 1549 with Palais-Royal (Paris) in the late eighteenth century, or Soho (London) in the 1860s. The apparent absence of prostitutes from half the districts of Rome suggests that the tax roll was compiled by collectors from the office responsible, i.e. the Corte Savella in Via di Monserrato, who already knew where to find the majority of prostitutes, and aimed to get the maximum revenue with the least effort. They did not always succeed; 22 women in the district of Ponte refused to pay (e.g. Appendix 1, n° 31-35). The absence of prostitutes from the district of Borgo is almost certainly results from a decision to insulate the adjoining Vatican from taint, rather than a fact.

The income of the prostitutes in 1549

The economic status of the women can be deduced from the annual rents they were assessed on, which ranged from 3 scudi (Appendix 1, n° 183 & 221) to as much as 150 scudi (n° 389). The distribution of rentals is shown in the histogram, Fig. 3. The median rent is 22 scudi, meaning that half of the women paid less than that. It is clear that those paying so little were occupying a single room in a two-room house because they were often described as living above a shop or workshop. As an example one can cite 'Lucretia da tioli [Tivoli] sopra al barbere' who paid 20 scudi (Appendix 1, n° 135). These women were **common prostitutes** (*meretrici*), not courtesans, despite the title of the roll. They numbered 218, forming half of all the prostitutes in the city. Their wretched style of life can, perhaps, be appreciated from Mayhew's detailed description of the prostitutes of Soho, in London, about 1860 (Mayhew 1861, vol. 4, p. 358).

Two-roomed houses abound in the earlier 1527 census of Rome, for example 'Madona Vanoza madre del duca Valentino una casa partita in 3 poteghe et 3 habitation de sop[ra]'. The three lower rooms are described as workshops for the craftsmen who lived in them. Two of the upper rooms were occupied by prostitutes, and one by a 'poor old woman' (Armellini 1882, p. 73). Rome in 1549 still had many two-room houses. Those which survived until the 1820 *Catasto Gregoriano* can be easily identified, for though only 5 or 6 m wide, they have two doors with separate street numbers. One door opened into the ground floor room, and the other gave on to a wooden staircase leading to the upper room. Almost all have been super-elevated, but one minute two-story building of this kind can still be seen at 66/67 Via del Governo Vecchio, in Parione. The courtesan Julia da Gallese (†1565) owned a building like this at n° 89/90 Via dell'Arancio, in Campo Marzio, which she rented out to other prostitutes (Stewart 2025b).

The **courtesans** in the tax roll, arbitrarily defined here as those assessed on rentals of at least 22 scudi per year, numbered 218. For example, the celebrated courtesan Isabella de Luna owned a large house with an assessed rental of 100 scudi (Appendix 1, n° 301) valued at 2500 scudi when she died in 1564 (Pecchiai 1948, p. 316; Pallavicino 1573). Women like this had some control over their destinies, unlike the *meretrici*. Burchard in 1498 called them *cortegiane honeste*

(Burchard 1884, vol. 2, pp. 442–443), presumably because they had no need to resort to trickery to make a living. Today, the common view of Roman prostitutes comes from the courtesans, as in Caravaggio's paintings of Fillide Melandroni and Georgina Masson's captivating book.

The juxtaposition of prostitutes that can be detected in the 1549 tax roll for Rome shows that they were lining certain streets, like other professional workers. For example, six women in Via dei Coronari (Ponte) are described in the manuscript tax roll as living next to each other (Appendix 1, n° 40–45). Another four women in Campo Marzio living in Piazza Sant'Agostino are described in the same way (Appendix 1, n° 308–311). Juxtaposition of female-headed households is also seen in the 1527 census of Rome, for example Campo Marzio (Lee 1985, n° 1706–1711) and Ponte (Lee 1985, n° 3272–3278). Streets lined by prostitutes are also apparent in the Florentine census of 1561 (Kerton-Johnson 2022, Fig. 7).

The only courtesans whose charges are known, viz. Isabella de Luna (†1564) and Julia da Gallese (†1565), both expected 10 gold scudi a day from their clients, which accords with what Brantôme found when he visited Rome in 1560 (Brantôme 1876, p. 146). Montaigne, who visited Rome about 1580, quotes 1–4 scudi, presumably for common prostitutes, i.e. *meretrici* (Montaigne 1889, p. 302). Similar figures come from Venice at this time (Romei 2020). Considering that the scudo contained 3g of gold with a present-day value of about 150 euros, a charge of 10 scudi seems a lot. It was. The only men who could afford to pay so much were a select group of merchants, bankers, noblemen and rich foreign travellers. The correspondence of courtesans (Romano 1990) and other evidence (e.g. Bandello 1554, *novella* 51) does not show that priests and prelates predominated among the clients of prostitutes, despite the affirmations of Gnoli (1938, p. 197) and Delumeau (1959, vol. 1, p.422).

The annual income enjoyed by the courtesan Isabella de Luna was about 300 scudi (Stewart 2025b), while her assessed rental was 100 scudi (Appendix 1, n° 301). Julia da Gallese had an annual income of about 100 scudi and was assessed on a rental of 40 scudi (Appendix 1, n° 145). There are no income data for the renowned courtesan Tullia d'Aragona. However the 40 scudi of assessed rent (Appendix 1, n° 116) together with the inventory of her possessions (Grandinelli 1556), suggest an income similar to that of Julia da Gallese. The foregoing details, albeit sketchy, suggest that the annual income of courtesans was roughly three times the rent they were assessed on in 1549. This accords with the ratio between income and rents of present-day families of modest income, which is probably the best comparison available (Hulchanski 1994).

An idea of the economic status of Roman prostitutes, both *meretrici* and courtesans, can be had by comparing their incomes with those of their contemporaries in the city. The annual salary of a domestic servant was about 15–20 scudi in 1549, including maintenance (Stewart 2025b). A university teacher in the university of Rome at this time got about 300 scudi per year (Renazzi 1803, vols. 1 & 2), while a member of the nobility would have a net annual income from 1000 scudi upwards (Stewart 2023, p. 50; Stewart 2025a, p. 28; Delumeau 1957, vol. 1, pp. 469–472). A courtesan was vastly better off than a servant, but this was not the case with common prostitutes, or *meretrici*, some of whom were apparently earning less than servants.

The effect of prostitution on the Roman economy

In 1549 the total rent assessed on Roman prostitutes was 9636 scudi (Appendix 1). Using the relation between income and rental just described we get an aggregate annual income of 28900 scudi, or about 78 scudi per year per woman. The same procedure for Campo Marzio leads to a very similar result. The figure of 78 scudi is, of course, an average. For courtesans alone the annual income rises to 114 scudi, like that of the courtesan Julia da Gallese (see above).

Assuming that the money earned in Campo Marzio by the 185 resident prostitutes was all spent within the district, it would have provided the remaining 775 households with some 20 scudi annually, not far off the income of an average family. In other words, the economy of that district could have been almost totally supported by prostitution. To a more limited extent the same was true for other districts well populated by prostitutes. They were a significant economic force. It is hardly surprising, therefore, that the pope found almost insurmountable opposition to his plans to eject all the prostitutes from central Rome in 1566 (Mantioni 2016, p. 110).

The 1549 list of prostitutes compared with the 1527 census of Rome

The 1527 census of Rome has been used to estimate the number of prostitutes in the city and it is, therefore, worth comparing the figures obtained for 1527 with those of 1549 to see what, if anything, can be deduced.

The 1527 census lists only 29 courtesans (*cortigiane*) and a few whores (*puttane*), surely an underestimate, so some other way has to be found to count them. A technique used by Gnoli (1941), repeated by Delumeau in 1957 (1957, vol. 1, p. 421), and most recently by Mantioni (2016, p. 45) is to identify prostitutes by their names. So, in addition to the few women declaring themselves courtesans, Mantioni counted women who provided no place of origin (10%), as well as those who did, such as ‘Caterina pedimontana’ (90%). The assumption was that the specification of a place of origin was indicative of a prostitute (Mantioni 2016, pp. 31-32). Women stating a profession, widows and noblewomen were presumably left out of account. It must be pointed out, however, that most of the Roman population in the sixteenth century lacked a surname. An analysis of the 1527 census for the wealthy district of Pigna shows that only 20% of the inhabitants had surnames, and in Trastevere it was only 12%. It is clear from the census that both men and women overcame this identity problem by stating either a profession, or a place of origin, as, for example, in the following extract of names and serial numbers from the census of Ponte (Lee 1985, p. 60):

2556	Diana napolitana
2557	Urbano ferrarese
2558	Io. Angelo piemonteso
2559	Antonia lavandara
2560	Francisca paduana
2561	Tasino hosto
2562	Ioanna fiorentina
2563	Diego spagnolo

Those few men and women who stated no place of origin may have been in doubt about where it really was. Nineteenth century census returns, for example, reveal a surprising number of individuals who provided different birth places in successive censuses.

There is no additional documentary information about the individuals in the list above, so why should any of them be prostitutes? The conclusion must be that the identification of prostitutes by their names alone is not feasible, as long ago pointed out by Partner (1976, p. 98).

Another problem with estimating the number of prostitutes in 1527 is that many may have been hidden in brothels. Consider, for example, *madonna Silvia* in Parione with 31 other occupants (Lee 1985, n° 4476), and *Madonna Incoronata* in Monti with 16 more occupants (Lee 1985, n° 388). These women lacked a surname, indicating that they were not noblewomen. Nor were they likely to be legitimate businesswomen because a glance at the lists of craftsmen and shop keepers in the census shows that they hardly ever had more than 9 employees (Lee 1985, pp. 322–356). Madonna Silvia and Madonna Incoronata were probably, but not certainly, brothel owners.

Table 1. Female-headed households (FHH) in sixteenth century Rome and Florence.

	Population	Households	FHH	%	Source
Rome (1527)	53689	9328	2058	22	Lee (1985)
Florence (1561)	59216	8691	1297	15	Kerton-Johnson et al. (2022, p. 84)

A more fruitful approach to the question of prostitution is to simply count the number of households in 1527 which were headed by a woman (FHH). This is a reliable, well-known technique of social analysis with a substantial literature (e.g. Trias-Prats & Esteve 2024). The proportion of FHH in the Roman population in 1527 was by no means unusual. It compares quite well with that for Florence in 1561 (Table 1) and with European societies in recent centuries (Hufton 1984). However, a closer look at the numbers of FHH in the various districts of Rome shows some striking anomalies (Table 2). The unusually high percentages for the northern districts, particularly Campo Marzio, would today be correlated with poverty (cf. Saad et al. 2022). This is because the men who would have been expected to support the families are absent, leaving the women, generally less well educated, less skilled, and underpaid, to cope alone, often with dependants. However, this picture of distress conflicts with the evidence of district wealth.

Table 2. Female headed households in Rome in 1527

District	Households	FHH	%
Campo Marzio	1068	458	43
Borgo	563	170	30
Ponte	1446	393	27
Sant'Eustachio	432	115	27
Regola	1178	285	24
Pigna	377	69	18
Colonna	510	93	18
Monti	476	75	16
Trevi	372	57	15
Trastevere	824	109	13
Sant'Angelo	597	76	13
Campitelli	251	29	11.5
Parioni	909	98	11
Ripa	325	31	9.5
Total	9328	2058	22

The total number of households in each district comes from Lee (1985, p. 20). FHH is the number of female headed households in each district.

Wealth in 1527 can be roughly estimated by identifying the districts where cardinals lived, all concentrated in the northern part of the city, near the Vatican, as shown in Fig. 1. The retinues of the pope and his cardinals, mainly unmarried men, comprised 5% of the city population at that time and were then one of the main supports for the city economy. Not only that, but the nobility of Rome preferred to live in the same districts. In Pigna, for example, Cardinal Pisano had a retinue of 130 people, but the two noble families Altieri and Astalli had between them retinues totalling another 235. Although Cardinal Pisano's presence was brief, the Altieri and the Astalli remained important families in Pigna for centuries longer.

As can be seen from Table 2, the FHH in areas of Rome *without* resident cardinals ranged from 10% to 16%, whereas in areas *with* cardinals it was much higher, ranging from 18% to 30%. Campo Marzio, however, appears to be quite anomalous. It had no cardinals and hardly any nobles in 1527. At that time, clerics and nobles in Campo Marzio together formed only 16% of the district population, whereas Borgo and Sant'Eustachio had 51% and 47%, respectively (Lee 1985, pp. 359-361). Campo Marzio only started to gain wealthy residents in 1550, following the efforts of the popes Giulio III and Paolo III to develop the district.

The northward increase in the percentage of female-headed households found in the Rome of 1527 correlates closely with northwardly increasing numbers of prostitutes in 1549, both reaching a peak in Campo Marzio. It appears that the high percentages of FHH in the northern districts of Rome in 1527 stemmed not from poverty, but from wealth based on prostitution.

The convent of the Convertite

As explained earlier, this convent was established in 1520 by pope Leo X to house repentant prostitutes, financed by a death duty levied on their unrepentant sisters. The duty appears to have been based on the observation that some of the active women appeared to be very wealthy.

By 1527 there were already 58 residents in the new convent, though presumably not all were nuns (Lee 1985, p. 46, n° 1251). Fifty years later, in 1572, there were about 150 women, judging from the daily consumption of 117 litres of wine and 6 litres of olive oil (Pallavicino 1572). By 1625 the number of nuns had increased further still, to 194 (including 21 *converse*) and the annual income to 5700 scudi (Liroso 2010, p. 250, note 805).

The pope's initiative was clearly successful as an institutional project, but much less so financially. In 1572 the death duty contributed only 686 scudi to the convent's total income of 3993 scudi. Most of the money to support the institution came from the pope, his cardinals, and other charities connected with the Roman church. Legacies totalled 345 scudi, while recurrent income from land and property belonging to the convent was only 160 scudi (Pallavicino 1572).

The pope and his advisors seem not to have considered the likely mortality of prostitutes, or their wealth at death. An order of magnitude estimate of mortality can be had by comparing Rome in the sixteenth century with an under-developed country, for example Guyana in 2002. In Guyana the specific death rate for women in the age range 20–30 years was 0.002 deaths per year, or slightly less than one death a year in a group of 436 young women (Beaie 2008, Table 1). Furthermore, in Rome it was only the courtesans who could conceivably have been wealthy when they died. In fact, of the total death duty of 686 scudi collected in 1572, no less than 620 scudi came from the duty levied on the estate of just one courtesan, Isabella de Luna (Pallavicino 1573). The premise behind the foundation of the convent of the Convertite, that it could be financed by a tax on working prostitutes, was just a fantasy.

Conclusions

The wealth of Roman courtesans (as defined above) was not what it seemed because generally their income was transformed into finery rather than into investments. But their choice of career, despite its risks, made sense economically when considering the bleak alternatives. No wife, servant or washerwoman would be able to have an income comparable with a courtesan, or indeed some *meretrici*. Nor would she have had the same degree of freedom.

The price of all this was set out in a letter by Veronica Franco, the renowned Venetian courtesan, written to the mother of a girl considering a career in prostitution (Franco 1580, pp. 44–45). To begin with, Franco writes, prostitution is a highly dangerous profession, with the risk of violence, robbery and even death. Secondly, it is a kind of psychological slavery, for the woman has to continually mirror her client's desires, whatever they are. Finally, there is the serious risk of contracting a horrible disease (syphilis). Much has changed in the last 500 years, but even now a prostitute's risk of being murdered is 100 times greater than for any other woman (Potterat et al. 2004).

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Appendix 1. Annual assessed rents of Roman prostitutes in 1549

Archivio di Stato, Roma, Camerale I, fabbriche,
busta 1514 fascicolo 18, ff. 1r-16v

<i>f. 1r</i>		scudi	<i>f. 2v</i>		scudi
	Ponte			a Sta simone	
1	Silvia ferrarese	30	35	Angelicha	
2	Luvisa ciciliana	12	36	Francesca spagniola	12
3	Chiecina fiorentina	13	37	Camilla milanese	30
4	Julia vinisiana	33	38	Lucretia da monte ritondo	20
			39	Regina tudescha	10
	Da torre de' nona		40	Julia bolognese	
5	Eugenia	26	41	Julia	10
6	Geronima romana		42	Chiecha fiorentina	12
7	Salustia	26	43	Fantinella	88
8	Vitoria sanese	33	44	Galicia napolitana	28
9			45	Isabella portogese	
11	Inzabella spaniolla elle figlie	36	<i>f. 3r</i>		
12	Francesca sanese		46	Bianca milanese	18
<i>f. 1v</i>			47	Lucia fiorentina	12
	nella strada diretto a S^{to} Salvatore de Laura			Dal Re^{mo} medici alla fiametta	
13	Francesca Sainedra spaniola	30	48		
14	Speranza spaniola		49	Antonia grecha [e] Cipriana romana	20
15	Nicoletta genovese		50	Giovanna ferarese	20
16	Nina da Porto	33	51	Camilla sanese	40
17	Isabella vinisiana	33	52	Giovanna napolitana	33
18	Margaritta vinisiana	16	53		
19	Lucretia aretina		54	Libera e Anna sorelle franzese	40
20	Verginia sfregata		55		15
21	Isabella spaniola	40	56	Laura ferarese	
22	Lucretia perugina	36	57		25
23	Lisabetta		58	Isabella napolitana	60
<i>f. 2r</i>				nella strada della madre di sermonette	
24	Camilla sanese		59	Paula spagniola	34
	Alla piazza de s^{to} salvatore de' lauro		60	Virginia da viterbo	18
25	Calidonia	26	61	Faustina	
26	Francesca fiorentina	12	62	Antonia compagna	25
	de dietro a s^{to} salvatore de' lauro		<i>f. 3v</i>		
27	Calidonia		63	Jovanna franzese	20
28	Margaritta romana	12	64	Diamante da urbino	20
	Dal l'arco de parma		65	Madalena bolognese alias la pulitta	33
29	Giovanna romana		66	Margarita todescha	14
30	Giovanna bolognese	40	67	Sandra	33
31	Anna spaniola			A l'orsso presso la scroffa	
32	Ipolitta bella gamba		68	Gentile romagnolla	33
33	Cassandra ferrarese		69	Concordia, sorella della Gentile	22
34	Margharitta picicarola				

70	Lucretia bolognese	35	116	Tulia d'Ara[g]onia	40
71	Antonia fiorentina	33	117	Ortenzia grecha	40
72	Isabella todescha	40	118	Anna bolognese	
73	Catarina grecha	33	119	Anna bolognese	20
74	Lucia sanese	16	120	Agniola bolognese	33
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<i>f. 4r</i>			<i>f. 5v</i>		
75	Isabella genovese	40	121		34
76		18	122	Pante perugina	33
77	Isabella paduana	55	123	Iovanna vignarola	35
78	Lena sartorella	40	124		
			125	Lucia catalena [e] Agnola morena	33
			126	Diamante padoanna	18
	Dalla stufa de'done				
79	Paulla venetiana	12			
80	Diamante			A monte citorio	
81	Beatrisse spagniola		127	Flaminia romana	40
82	Bernardina	12	128		
83	Bettina fiorentina		129	figlie della Maddalena da tioli [Tivoli]	33
			130		
			131	Portia romana e sua sorella	40
	nel vicolo a fronte alla paduana		132	Caterina da tioli	32
84	Margaritta luchese	18			
85				Nella strada per andare allo	
86	Faustina [e] Adriana figlie	20		abassatore de francia	
87	Lucretia	35	133	Caterina da urbino	22
88	Lucia	18	134	fiorentina	25
			135	Lucretia da tioli	20
<hr/>					
<i>f. 4v</i>			<i>f. 6r</i>		
89			136	Silvia camiciara	40
92	Angela [e] Filippa				
93	Cornelia	33		diretto al sor torgnato [Torquato]	
94	Camilla	8	137	Isabella di vosto	50
95	Laura spagniola	34			
96	Margaritta perugina	33		Dalla strada dello abasatore di francia	
97	Margaritta romana	35	138	Jacopa romana	33
98			139	Margarita	20
99	Maria [e] Maria	33	140	Ausilia	12
100	Maria fiamengha	33	141	Camilla bolognese	33
101	Polisena grecha		142	Agnola de sinibaldi	28
102	Agniola spagniola	38	143	Ippolita furlana	35
103	Caterina spagnola		144	Isabella	33
104	Rodericha spagniola		145	Giulia da galese	40
105	Agniola Spagniola	16	146	Costanza napolitana	40
			147	Tulia da formello	24
			148	Giovia allias la zoppetta	50
<hr/>					
<i>f. 5r</i>			<i>f. 6v</i>		
106	viniciana	25		In su la piassa di san Lorenzo in Lucina	
107	Lucretia della paduana	18	149	Leria todescha	35
			150	Danora	25
	Alla scrofa sopra la Spiciaria		151 152	Lisabetta ella madre	20
108	Casandra viniciana	50			
109				diretto alla scoparolla	
111	Laurina viniciana ella madre e sua sorella		153		12
80			154	Faustina scoparola	25
112	Caterina ferarese	32	155	Camilla piemontese	12
113	Speranza franzese	18	156	Giovanna franscese	12
114					
	Nel vicolo drietto a Casali				
115	Antonia e Nicolosa bolognese	16			

Nella strada de'pontifici			Dal R^{mo} Calone e prima diretto		
238	Laldonia	50	279	Ippolita de pelestrina	10
239	Briandia	80	280	Moretta	20
240	Lucia spagniola	40	281	Pantasilena	20
241	Gieronima	35	282	Julia	8
242	Gioma [Gironima] alberina	33	283		8
243	Dianora de pratis	50	284	Antonia balerina	8
<i>f. 10^r</i>			285	Isabella giudea fatta cristiana	9
244	Chiechina fiorentina	35	<i>f. 11^v</i>		
Nella strada de s^{to} Jacomo			286		9
245	Camiletta bolognese	40	287		9
246		24	288	Gieronima da Castello	8
247	Vergilia alberina	34	289		10
Nella strada diretta del popolo			290	Lauura viterbese	12
248	Diamante spadara	15	291	Dianora aquilana	11
249	Laura ferrarese	15	292	Lucretia napoletana	15
250	Trentina	50	In colone		
251	Angelicha bolognese	18	293	Ipolita modanina	40
252	Maria	15	294		15
253			Nel vicolo degli ogliarari de Capranica		
254	Antonia e Margaritta bichierare	40	295	Martta	34
255	Caterinna pistolesse	32	296	Bl ^{ma} Sfrexiatta	18
256	Lucretia ferra[rese]	40	297	Aurelia	
<i>f. 10^v</i>			<i>f. 12^r</i>		
nella strada dritta del popolo			298	Livia romana	24
257	Catterina balarina	10	299	Speransa spagnola	8
258		15	300	Dianora ciciliana	40
259		12	301	Isabella de Luna spagniola	100
260			302	Franceschigia morena	84
261	Vienna Veronese [e] sua madre	25	303	Lucretia piemontese o romana	33
262	Antonina alias la pupa	20	304	Isabella spagniola	40
263			305	Caterina ferarese	34
265	Margaritta Serristora, Tina ella madre	15	In su la piassa de s^{to} augustino		
266	Caterina genovese	8	306	Filippa	20
267	Carolina	8	307	Spagniola	15
268	Caterina spadara	33	308	Paulla bolognese	25
269	Agnese	20	<i>f. 12^v</i>		
270		25	309	Lucretia schiavona	25
a fronte della crose della trinità			310	Isabella	15
271	Ludovica bolognese	20	311	Carolina tudescha	15
272	Ipolita da gavignano	14	312	Nastasia	18
<i>f. 11^r</i>			313	Apolonia	2
273	Julia	20	In torre Sanguigna		
274	Insabella del Tuffo napoletana	33	314	Ipolitta romana	25
275	Angelica vinisiana	20	315	Dianora	25
Nella strada nova della trinità			316		
276	Catarina spagnola	25	317	Camilla paduana e Antonia senese	33
277			318	Isabella	24
278	Aquilina ella figlia	25	319	Carolina todescha	15

Nel vicolo della passe di verso sanguigna		359	
320	Cornelia ciciliana	40	360 Nera pitolese e Carolina sua madre
321	Stella veneciana	16	361 Carolina macelara
<hr/>			362 Antonia sanese
<i>f. 13r</i>			363 Agnesa bolognese
322	Antonia francese grassa	22	364
323	Agnola	12	<hr/>
da Loste della golpe		<i>f. 14v</i>	diretto alla Luchina
324		20	365
325	Faustina culdorse	18	366 Julia ella madre greche
326	Julia ferrarese	18	367 Margaritta
327	Maria della riga spagnola	44	368 Lucia
328	Michella	40	
329	Isabella	40	Diretto al paone
330	Lucida o Lucia	34	369 Turchetta
331		20	370 Lucia sugerella
332	Carolina grecha	60	371 Agniola
			372 Lucretia grecha
A fronte alla Giovanna Ventura			Alla chiavica de S^a Lucia
333	Portia napolitana	40	373 Ipolitta perugina
334	Antea	44	374 Camilla mantovana
335	Livia bolognese	55	375 Giovanna bolognese
<hr/>			
<i>f. 13v</i>			In strada Julia
336	Susanna	50	376 Graziosa milanese
337	Francesca della riga	44	<hr/>
338	Costanza fiorentina	50	<i>f. 15r</i>
339	Diana	13	377
			378 Julia perugina [e] Susanna sua madre
	Nella strada nova de panigi		379 Porsia napolitana
340	Silvia	20	
	diretto a banchi		nel vicolo de casali a fiume
341	Moretta	12	380 Umana de urbino
342	Carolina bolognese	5	381 Fiora da urbino
343	Portia naso spicato	12	382 Agnesa
344	Laura vinisiana	33	383 Marsia
345	Margarita ferarresse	40	384 Laura viniciana
346		18	385 Laura
347			386 Saltarella
348	Palcida ella madre	33	387 Rosatta perugina
<hr/>			
<i>f. 14r</i>			Apresso alla s. a. dogna Madalena
	In strada Paulina		388 Penelope
349		22	<hr/>
350		12	<i>f. 15v</i>
351	Paula	22	Seguita in strada Julia
352			389 Maddalenna spagniola
353	Margaritta fiorentina [e] sua compagna	20	390 Isabella mantovana
354			391 Nicola fransese
355	Gentile [e] Antonia	10	392 Cornelia
356	Serena	20	
	In strada Jullia		Nelle casse piccole delli eleni
357	Paulla viniciana	40	393 Caterina ferarese
358	Luchina	60	394

395	Margaritta todescha	12			
396	Lucia perugina	12			
397	Julia napolitana	50			
398	Pierra	11			
399	Catarina	12			
<hr/>					
<i>f. 16r</i>					
400	Giovanna francese	16			
401	Caterina	12			
402	Proserpina da Pisa	12			
403	Medea	15			
404	Giovanna fiamingha	16			
405	Agnesina piacentina	20			
406	Nastasia	12			
407	Caterina mantovana	22			
408		9			
Diretta al palazzo Farnese in via Julia					
409	Caterina parmisana	25			
410	Antonia milanese	10			
411	Veronica				
412		12			
Diretto al comandante da fiume					
413	Prudenzia fiorentina	9			
414	Betta da colle	6			
415		6			
Da nasono					
416	Lucia parmisana	34			
				nella strada da s^{to} pantaleo a farnese	
417	Cencia vennesiana		35		
418	Jovana spagniola		100		
Da navona alla sapienza					
419	Doralice		50		
420	Lucia romana		50		
421	Tina polarola [pollaiola]		30		
422	Gostanza		30		
Di raso alle fratte delle valle					
423	Porzia		36		
424	Martina vinisiana		16		
Dalla ciambella					
425	Pantasilea romana		35		
<hr/>					
<i>f. 16v</i>					
alla stufa de passini					
426	Proserpina romana		20		
427	Giovanna		9		
428	Vit.a		6		
429	Julia fiamingha		25		
Dalla Madalena verso Capranica					
430	Apolonia		12		
431					
432	Lucrezia da montefiascone [e] Moretta.		15		
433					
434	Julia vinisiana [e] Barbera todesca		12		
435					
436	Girolama spagiola [e] Crestina		16		

The name of each woman is preceded by a serial number, followed by her place of origin and the annual rent she was assessed on, in *scudi*. The date of the tax roll is stated to be 1549 on *f. 16v*. For facsimilies of the pages, wrongly collocated, see Mendoza (2016, pp. 41–74, transcribed on pp. 229–261).